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Impact Factor: 3.43

Cite this paper as : Preetinder Kaur & Sukhvir Singh (2017), "CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AND VOLUNTARY INFORMATION DISCLOSURE", *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management*, ISSN: 2348 –3954 (online) ISSN: 2349 –2546 (print), Volume 5,(Issue 5,May-2017), pp 12-19,

CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AND VOLUNTARY INFORMATION DISCLOSURE

Ms Preetinder Kaur *

Dr. Sukhvir Singh **

*Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Hans Raj College, University of Delhi, Delhi.

**Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, SGTB Khalsa College, University of Delhi, Delhi.

ABSTRACT

Under the regime of corporate governance Indian regulatory authorities are keeping update of disclosure practices to ensure the transparency, true and fair disclosure in corporate reporting. The stakeholders are also considering the true and fair corporate financial reporting as an important parameter for their analysis. The most reliable channel for this reporting is taken as published annual reports. In these annual reports corporates are disclosing all the mandatory information, but along with the mandatory information the corporates are also providing voluntary information, which is highly considered by the users. This paper has tried to examine the level of corporate disclosure on the basis of information disclosed voluntarily in the published annual reports. The Study was based on firms listed on S&P CNX Nifty. The final sample consists of published annual reports of 50 companies which were studied for a period of five years that is 2011-2016. The study concluded that these large cap companies give more importance to financial nature items, limited number of companies have considered other items of the index for voluntary disclosure .On the basis of statistical analysis the study has also concluded that no company has reached to the disclosure of more than 100 items. There is a slight change in the yearly mean disclosure of the companies.

Key words - corporate disclosure, Published Annual Reports, general corporate information

Introduction:

Corporate disclosure is considered as a mirror of soul of the firm. How much firm is transparent about its financial health? The answer to this question is given by the firm at its own by providing information disclosure. These days' stakeholders are not only considering the financial health but also activities related to non -financial aspects. As most of the corporate governance failures worldwide have been attributed to poor disclosure practices, many of the reforms at the national and international level have focused on the improvement of corporate disclosure practices. There are number of media channels through which corporate information can be disclosed by the firms. But review of literature provides the view that annual reports are most used source of information in the eyes of the stakeholders. This research work is an attempt to derive a view about the disclosure practices of the corporate world and annual reports were considered as an information source here to analyze the disclosure practices of the firms.

Buzby (1974) concluded that the companies should give due consideration to information needs of the users of financial statements while deciding on the items to be included in the annual reports. The study observed that there existed a case for expansion in the extent of disclosure in the annual reports of small and medium sized companies.

Rathinam (1996) has made a comprehensive study about disclosure practices of Indian companies. Using an index of disclosure consisting of 114 items, he measured the disclosure of statutory and voluntary items of information in the annual reports of 160 companies - 146 private sector and 14 public sector companies, He also he examined the relationship between various corporate attributes and disclosure, and analysed disclosure practices of companies regarding certain contemporary issues in financial reporting like Social Responsibility Accounting, Human Resource Accounting, Value Added Statement etc. Thereafter, he collected data from three user groups -corporate executives, corporate auditors and investors through 3 sets of questionnaires. The study revealed that companies give more emphasis on the disclosure of statutory information. The voluntary information is not given significant attention by the companies.

The special statements like HRA, VAS and SRA are not found to present except in a few cases. Companies, which belong to different age, profitability, asset size, turnover and existence of collaboration, have different disclosure scores.

Balasubramaniam (2010) showed that the Disclosure of a firm (Financial or non -Financial) could be mandatory or discretionary. Mandatory disclosures are information provided under certain statutory requirements and are intended to provide only minimum quantity of information necessary of decision making. They are subject to verification, evaluation and certification by the independent auditors or legal counsel in terms of content and/or process.

Sarkar (2011) showed that there was 100 percent disclosure for mandatory items but wide diversity in the type and presentation of voluntary disclosure among companies. He suggested a common framework for presentation of information in the annual reports to meet the test of comparability and said that failures should also be reported in the annual reports.

Charumathi and Latha (2015) explore the factors that determine the voluntary disclosure choices of the non-financial companies listed in the National Stock Exchange (NSE). The study uses a voluntary disclosure index (VDI) constructed by the authors with 81 financial and non-financial items across different categories such as strategy, forward looking, environment and social, etc. With the VDI, this study measures the voluntary disclosure levels for four financial years from 2009–2010 to 2012–2013 using the content analysis methodology. The study uses a panel data model to analyze the effects of three categories of variables, namely, firm characteristics, profitability and governance and found the fixed effect model to be suitable and leverage, size and institutional ownership emerged as the determinants of voluntary disclosures. The study revealed that the regulators and the capital market are increasingly imposing stringent norms for transparency. It can be observed from the fact that the items, which were voluntary few years back, have become mandatory. The corporate India has the onus of ensuring better compliance and reporting standards to increase the capital market prospects.

Elamagrhi et al (2016) suggested that there is a substantial variation in the levels of compliance with, and disclosure of, good CG practices among the sampled UK firms. The authors also find that firms with larger board size, more independent outside directors and greater director diversity tend to disclose more CG information voluntarily, whereas the level of voluntary CG compliance and disclosure is insignificantly related to the existence of a separate CG committee and institutional ownership. Additionally, the results indicate that block ownership and managerial ownership negatively affect voluntary CG compliance and disclosure practices. The findings are fairly robust across a number of econometric models that sufficiently address various endogeneity problems and alternative CG indices. Overall, the findings are generally consistent with the predictions of neo-institutional theory.

In the context of the idea generated from the literature review, the research was initiated with the objective to know the level of voluntary disclosure about the corporate information. For this research purpose sample size was analyzed thoroughly, the analysis which is based on the specified objective, that was the examination of the level of disclosure of items on the disclosure index.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study is based on the objective to know the Level of Voluntary Disclosure of the corporate information through their published annual reports.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The Research design is descriptive and based on data available from secondary sources. The sample frame comprised of most liquid firms listed on S&P CNX NIFTY, India. The final sample consisted of 50 companies and period of study was five years, from 2011-2016.

For examination of voluntary disclosure various items of financial and non- financial information were selected from annual reports of different companies on random selection basis. The published annual reports are considered as the most important parameter for disclosure of information by the corporates. Hence other disclosure methods like Prospectus, Press releases, house magazines, periodicals, statutory reports and interim reports publications of professional and other accounting bodies, official reports and publications of stock exchanges have not been considered in the present study. After detailed study on the annual reports of various companies, Disclosure index was prepared and in total 108 numbers of items were shortlisted as items, which are disclosed voluntarily by the firms to serve the requirements of Indian Capital Market. Descriptive Statistical tools were applied to examine the extent of such disclosure. Each item in the index of disclosure has been assigned a score of either 0 or 1, if an item has been disclosed in the annual report of the company; the item is assigned with a score of 1. In case of non-disclosure of the item, score 0 is given. The score sheet was prepared on the basis of given scores separately for each published annual reports for the years 2011-12, 2012-13, 2013-14, 2014-15, 2015-16. Further statistical tools were applied to get a result from the score sheet.

ANALYTICAL TOOLS USED FOR THE STUDY: Descriptive Statistical tools like Arithmetic Mean, Standard Deviation and co-efficient of variations, tables and diagrams were applied to examine the extent of voluntary disclosure made by the firms.

ANALYSIS OF ITEM -WISE DISCLOSURE

As per the objective of the study, examination was done on the extent of item-wise disclosure of the firms of sample size. The purpose behind this examination was to examine the extent of corporates disclosure of various items on a voluntary basis to serve the information requirements of the stakeholders.

After scanning the Annual Reports of the Companies, disclosure index was prepared which comprises 108 items in total. To check the level of disclosure, these 108 numbers of items were considered. The item wise disclosure was computed by dividing average disclosure made by all the companies with number of total companies in the sample, and yearly percentage disclosure was obtained. Table 4.1 highlights the item wise disclosure of annual reports. This also gives a mean disclosure for all the five years for the total period of the study.

Table 1.1: Item wise Disclosure of Firms

ITEM- WISE DISCLOSURE IN ANNUAL REPORTS						
Items of Information	Disclosing Companies for different years in percentage					Mean Disclosure in %
	2011 -12	2012 -13	2013 -14	2014 -15	2015 -16	
General Corporate Information						
1. Brief history of company	84	82	60	84	84	78.8
2. Corporate mission statement	98	96	92	100	98	96.8
3. Organizational structure	90	98	98	94	94	94.8
4. Description of Goods and Services Produced	100	99	100	100	100	99.8
5. Description of marketing networks for goods and services	90	93	96	96	98	94.6
6. Stock Exchanges on which shares are listed.	100	97	100	100	98	99
7. Companies contribution to national economy	4	8	30	0	2	8.8
8. Statement of strategy and objectives - general	48	58	34	58	52	50
9. Statement of strategy and objectives - financial	38	32	52	44	64	46
10. Statement of strategy and objectives - marketing	38	32	40	42	42	38.8
11. Statement of strategy and objectives - social	36	30	42	42	40	38
12. Impact of strategy on current results	10	4	14	14	16	11.6
13. Impact of strategy on future results	2	0	8	2	6	3.6
14. Reasons for the acquisitions	68	60	58	64	58	61.6
15. Reasons for the disposals	66	60	64	66	54	62
16. Corporate policy on research and development	82	89	68	94	88	84.2
17. Location of research and development activities	24	15	36	18	16	21.8
18. Number employed in research and development	6	11	8	8	6	7.8
19. Qualitative forecast of sales	0	0	0	2	0	0.4
20. Quantitative forecast of sales	10	12	6	14	16	11.6
21. Qualitative forecast of profits	0	0	10	0	0	2
22. Quantitative forecast of profits	10	12	6	14	16	11.6
23. Qualitative forecast of cash flows	0	2	10	0	0	2.4
24. Quantitative forecast of cash flows	8	10	4	36	14	14.4
25. Assumptions underlying the forecasts	0	0	12	0	0	2.4
26. Current period trading results - qualitative	4	1	0	2	2	1.8
27. Current period trading results - quantitative	84	83	58	86	92	80.6
28. Order book or backlog information	0	0	26	0	0	5.2
29. Other useful information	0	0	0	0	0	0
30. Age and retirement age of the directors	82	85	68	78	78	78.2
31. Educational qualifications (academic and professional)	86	87	88	82	80	84.6
32. Commercial experience of the executive directors	90	93	88	92	88	90.2
33. List of Directors	100	97	98	98	98	98.2
34. Shares held by directors of the company	94	94	98	94	96	95.2
35. Remuneration of the directors	94	96	98	94	92	94.8
36. Functions of board	96	97	96	96	96	96.2

37. Meetings held and attended	100	97	96	96	96	97
38. Other directorships held by executive directors	88	76	70	76	70	76
39. Training of board members	8	12	38	10	6	14.8
40. Geographical distribution of employees	18	44	18	20	14	22.8
41. Line-of-business distribution of employees	10	14	12	10	30	15.2
42. Categories of employees by gender	48	42	34	50	48	44.4
43. Identification of senior management and their functions	8	4	16	4	6	7.6
44. Number of employees for two or more years	0	0	2	0	0	0.4
45. Reasons for changes in employee numbers or categories	0	0	0	0	0	0
46. Amount spent on training	6	8	4	6	2	5.2
47. Nature of training	14	12	0	8	6	8
48. Categories of employees trained	2	6	8	4	2	4.4
49. Number of employees trained	2	6	4	4	2	3.6
50. Data on accidents	0	0	0	0	0	0
51. Cost of safety measures	8	12	4	12	10	9.2
52. Redundancy information (general)	0	0	2	0	0	0.4
53. Equal opportunity policy statement	4	2	8	4	4	4.4
54. Recruitment problems and related policy	0	0	2	2	0	0.8
55. Safety of products (general)	76	93	64	98	92	84.6
56. Charitable donations (amount)	66	68	82	78	78	74.4
57. Community programs (general)	68	68	80	80	82	75.6
58. Value added statement	42	67	66	54	56	57
59. Value added data	40	45	56	46	50	47.4
60. Value added ratios	32	38	68	40	58	47.2
61. Qualitative value added information	12	24	20	6	14	15.2
62. Company concern for environment	70	76	64	88	88	77.2
63. Compliance with environmental Standards	14	14	30	26	18	20.4
64. Conservation of natural resources	26	28	30	38	36	31.6
65. Information relating to environmental costs and liabilities	20	20	20	16	18	18.8
66. Future estimates relating to environmental costs	14	10	14	8	8	10.8
67. Adoption of environment friendly technology	16	12	12	14	10	12.8
68. Training and education of employees on environment protection	2	4	12	4	2	4.8
69. Awards for environment protection	6	10	6	12	12	9.2
70. Other useful non- financial information	0	2	2	0	0	0.8
71. Graphic Or Diagrammatic presentation of Non -Financial Information	0	4	0	0	2	1.2
72. Segmental Information	94	99	72	100	94	91.8
73. Geographical capital expenditure - quantitative	10	6	32	10	22	16
74. Geographical production - quantitative	10	9	8	10	16	10.6
75. Line-of-business production - quantitative	14	7	4	14	16	11
76. Competitor analysis – qualitative	0	0	2	0	4	1.2
77. Competitor analysis - quantitative	0	0	0	0	4	0.8
78. Market share analysis - qualitative	0	0	0	0	2	0.4
79. Market share analysis - quantitative	2	0	0	0	2	0.8
80. Profitability ratios	86	89	70	92	90	85.4

81.	Cash flow ratios	86	89	92	92	92	90.2
82.	Liquidity ratios	88	93	92	92	92	91.4
83.	Gearing ratios	88	93	92	92	92	91.4
84.	Disclosure of intangible valuations (except goodwill and brands)	84	89	92	92	94	90.2
85.	Dividend payout policy	86	94	92	90	92	90.8
86.	Financial history or summary - six or more years	72	85	80	76	76	77.8
87.	Restatement of financial information to non-U.S./U.K. GAAP	76	80	86	74	64	76
88.	Off balance sheet financing information	16	50	44	22	14	29.2
89.	Advertising information - qualitative	0	2	10	10	2	4.8
90.	Advertising expenditure - quantitative	18	22	8	16	12	15.2
91.	Effects of inflation on future operations - qualitative	0	0	6	4	0	2
92.	Effects of inflation on results - qualitative	0	2	0	0	0	0.4
93.	Effects of inflation on results - quantitative	0	0	2	6	0	1.6
94.	Effects of inflation on assets - qualitative	0	0	0	0	0	0
95.	Effects of inflation on assets - quantitative	0	0	0	6	0	1.2
96.	Effects of interest rates on results	0	2	0	0	2	0.8
97.	Effects of interest rates on future operations	0	0	0	0	0	0
98.	Effects of foreign currency fluctuations on future operations – qualitative	18	24	14	20	16	18.4
99.	Effects of foreign currency fluctuations on current results – qualitative	28	28	24	32	22	26.8
100.	Major exchange rates used in the accounts	38	26	28	30	24	29.2
101.	Long-term debt by currency	44	44	42	46	38	42.8
102.	Short-term debt by currency	46	44	42	46	38	43.2
103.	Foreign currency exposure management description	20	16	26	18	12	18.4
104.	Market capitalization at year end	86	94	72	94	94	88
105.	Market capitalization trend	84	96	88	94	92	90.8
106.	Size of shareholdings	92	98	94	96	100	96
107.	Type of shareholder	90	96	94	92	96	93.6
108.	Graphic Presentation of Financial Information	98	99	100	94	98	97.8

A critical look of the table shows that around 15 numbers of items have been totally ignored by the companies in their annual report disclosure. These items are not considered as the information which should be passed to the users. Items like Qualitative forecast of sales, Number of employees for two or more years, amount spent on training of the employees, amount spent on safety from accidents, market share qualitative and quantitative analysis information, Effect of inflation on qualitative and quantitative results have been missed in disclosure content of the companies. Around 19 items have got disclosure in the annual reports of the all the companies of the sample. This shows that corporates want information of these 19 items should be shared with the users.

Having a close look of the environmental information disclosure by the companies, it was found that 77% companies were showing their concern about the environmental information disclosure in the annual reports; only 31% companies were providing information about the conservation of the natural resources. Whereas 9% companies were giving information about the awards they have been receiving for environment protection activities.

Taking into considerations the financial voluntary disclosure, almost all companies are considering that providing more and more information on the financial items is much more relevant than other items. It is very clear from the table here that voluntary disclosure on financial nature items have been made by more than 89 % of the firms. Inflation effect, change in interest rate effect, foreign currency fluctuation effect has been shown only by 10-20% companies. Market capitalization and types of shareholding information is provided by more than 90% of the companies.

Thus critical analysis of the item wise disclosure of the companies reveals that these large cap companies gives more importance to financial nature items, limited number of companies have considered other items of the index for voluntary disclosure.

VARIATION IN ITEM WISE -DISCLOSURE

To examine variation in item- wise disclosure of the annual reports for a period of five years, Table 1.2 has been prepared, which reveals degree of variation in disclosure of 108 items of these companies.

Table 1.2: Variations in Item-Wise Disclosure

Number of Disclosing Companies →	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16
Number of Items Covered ↓					
0-20	3	1	0	0	0
20-40	20	21	20	20	20
40-60	25	26	27	28	28
60-80	2	2	3	2	1
80-100	0	0	0	0	1
100-108	0	0	0	0	0
Mean Disclosure	40.4	41.6	43.2	42.8	43.2
S.D	13.41	12.06	11.74	11.14	12.4
Co-efficient of Variation	33.19	28.99	27.18	26.03	28.70

A cursory look of the above table shows that around 20 companies have shown 20-40 items in the index and 40-60 items have been shown by 25 to 28 companies. No company has reached to disclosure of more than 100 items. A slight change was found in the yearly mean disclosure of the companies. There is a variation of 13.41 items 2011-12 and 12.4 items in the year 2015-16 as suggested by value of standard deviation. Coefficient of variation comes to be very high in the year 2011-12 which was 33.19 per cent but in the following years it was significantly low as shown by results of the year 2015-16 where it was 28.7 per cent.

CONCLUSION:

As the number of corporates is increasing day by day worldwide, the investment market is also coming in focus and this has led to choice among the investors. When they have choice, they want full information before selecting particular group .Financial reporting has been considered as an important criterion for the financial analysis by the experts. The study concluded that the large cap companies gives more importance to financial nature items, limited number of companies have considered other items of the index for voluntary disclosure. On the basis of

statistical analysis the study has also concluded that no company has reached to disclosure of more than 100 items. There is a slight change in the yearly mean disclosure of the companies.

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